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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
WP	Work Package
SMS	Soil management strategies
C	Carbon
GHG	Greenhouse gases
Cseq	Carbon sequestration
N ₂ O	Nitrous oxide
NO ₃ ⁻	Nitrate
CH ₄	Methane
Yield	Crop yield
C/N ratio	Carbon to nitrogen ratio
CC	Cover crops
MODA	Multi-Objective Decision analysis
ANFIS	Adaptive-Network-based Fuzzy Inference System
VIW-RF	Variable Importance-Weighted Random Forests

ABSTRACT

The Σ OMMIT index will constitute a decision support tool to optimize soil management strategies (SMS, i.e., crop choice, fertilization, irrigation and tillage) according to their efficient contribution to carbon sequestration, taking into account associated non-CO₂ GHG emissions and productivity in a given agroecosystem. The objective of the Σ OMMIT index will be to evaluate alternative case scenarios, i.e., a combination of soil \times climate \times SMS, whose trade-off value will be translated into a score ranging from 0 to 1, i.e., higher index values indicate better trade-off. Carbon sequestration (Cseq), nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions, nitrate (NO₃⁻) leaching and crop yield (Yield) are the trade-off components under evaluation.

Two versions of the Σ OMMIT index have been designed and implemented by WP5. Both versions are structured in aggregation layers which synthesize the trade-off value of a case scenario and enable tracing back the contribution of SMS to the trade-off assessment, via the integration of fuzzy logic, machine learning and multi-objective decision analysis (MODA). They both implement a flexible weighting scheme to provide researchers and policy-makers with versatility when reflecting on their perception of system sustainability in the trade-off analysis. The main difference in the two versions is the level of implementation of expert opinion, either strong (version α) or light (version β), which translates into alternative algorithms used to aggregate basic input variables (Adaptive-Network-based Fuzzy Inference System in version α and Variable Importance-Weighted Random Forests in version β). The variables characterizing case scenarios as input to the two versions of the Σ OMMIT index were selected in compliance with Σ OMMIT Deliverable D2.1, in order to facilitate the ingestion of datasets from meta-analysis (WP2), long-term experiments (WP3) and simulation models (WP4). A template to characterize case scenarios has been released along with this report and is available [here](#).

The two versions Σ OMMIT index have been described and applied here on a dummy input dataset as a proof of concept. The results are brought to the attention of project partners, along with a prototype of online dashboard to test the efficacy of the two proposed solutions to perform trade-off analysis (available [here](#))

1. Introduction

1.1 Aim of this report

This report presents the work carried out by WP 5 to design the prototype of the Σ OMMIT index, which aims at identifying best trade-offs between Cseq, N₂O, NO₃⁻ and Yield under alternative SMS and considering the effects of pedo-environmental conditions. A proof of concept is given to explore the potential of two versions of the index to perform trade-off analyses using a dummy input dataset, and to highlight limits and improvement areas.

1.2 Background

Agriculture is among the human activities most affected by climate change (Rosenzweig et al., 2014) and at the same time the largest global contributor to anthropogenic non-CO₂ greenhouse gases (GHG) emissions (Syakila and Kroeze, 2011; Saunio et al., 2020). Agricultural soils are the major source of N₂O to the atmosphere, which contribution has gradually increased due to the massive use of N fertilizers and manure. Nonetheless, the estimation of the actual quote of global GHG emissions due to agricultural activities is subjected to large uncertainty (Ogle et al., 2005; Milne et al., 2015).

The fulfillment of the Sustainable Development Goals set within the UN 2030 Agenda requires taking informed decisions to promote effective climate change mitigation strategies (Fujimori et al., 2020). The legislation on agricultural GHG mitigation policies needs quantitative figures of the unintended positive and negative effects of SMS, in order to identify good practices for designing innovative and sustainable cropping systems, resilient to climate change impacts. Identifying co-benefits in the adoption of alternative SMS while unravelling their complex interactions with the overall system sustainability is needed to bridge gaps of knowledge and provide effective support to agricultural policy makers (Liu et al., 2019). Current knowledge indicates that the effect of SMS on soil carbon sequestration and GHG emissions is highly context-dependent, requiring a case-by-case evaluation to assess their interlinkages across pedo-environmental conditions (Abdalla et al., 2016; Sanz-Cobena et al., 2017; Shakoob et al., 2021). It has also been demonstrated that potential climate positive effects due to carbon farming can be offset by increased direct N₂O emissions (Lugato et al., 2018; Zhou et al., 2017). These studies did not consider indirect N₂O emissions, which could even tip the balance out of climate neutrality.

IPCC guidelines for National GHG Inventories (IPPC, 2006; IPCC, 2019) provide default equations and several emission factors for estimating carbon stock changes and N₂O emissions from agricultural soils consequent to fertilizations practices and nitrate leaching. These default equations and global emissions factors constitute the so-called Tier 1 methodologies, which allow evaluating CO₂ fluxes from SOC change, N₂O direct and indirect emissions from fertilization practices and the consequent net GHG emissions under a limited set of pedo-environmental and SMS conditions. Despite their main advantage of requiring a limited dataset, the major drawback of Tier 1 methodologies is the lack of explicit consideration of antagonistic and synergetic interactions among SMS, and between SMS and pedo-environmental conditions on yield and soil C and N cycles. The interdependent dynamics of soil carbon and nitrogen content are oversimplified by Tier 1 methodologies in the so called F_{SOM} factor, which accounts for an increase of a certain amount of N₂O emissions concurrently with a loss of carbon to keep constant the soil C:N ratio. Moreover, the complex processes at interplay within the Soil-Crop-Atmosphere nexus are weakly or not represented at all by Tier 1 methodologies. It is possible to overcome the simplification of Tier 1 methods using IPCC Tier 2 and Tier 3 methodologies (also referred as higher Tiers), which require the use of local emission factors or measurement/modelling approaches respectively (De Vries et al., 2005; Peter et al., 2016). However, to date the application of higher Tiers

is limited to research studies and initiatives, despite the high request from the public governmental institutions.

The most critical barrier to the wide adoption of every decision support tools is the capability to answer to real questions from users (Magarey et al., 2002). The integration of machine learning, fuzzy-logic and multi-criteria decision analysis to provide decision makers with useful and easy-to-use support tools has been pursued across fields like human health care (Nobre et al., 1999), urban regeneration (Morano et al., 2015), and agricultural sustainability assessment (Marks et al., 1995; Carozzi et al., 2013). The benefits of these methodologies rely in their capability to identify the most appropriate alternatives among predetermined ones, after evaluating them via traceable, data-based and transparent criteria (Kaya et al., 2019).

Σ OMMIT has mobilized expertise from several disciplines to deepen the comprehension of the interrelationships between carbon sequestration and greenhouse gases emissions, i.e., meta-analytic techniques to synthesize available research findings (WP 2), *ad hoc* field and laboratory experiments to complement existing datasets from long term field trials (WP 3) and process-based simulation modelling to perform scenario analyses on the effect of SMS on system sustainability (WP 4). The unique datasets which will be made available by the project need to be harmonized to develop a new trade-off assessment tool compliant with the requirements of IPCC Tier 3, embedding the effect of alternative SMS on carbon sequestration and GHG emissions. The Σ OMMIT index attempts to translate the knowledge and data produced by the other WPs into a tool usable by researchers and policy-makers to evaluate the trade-offs of alternative SMS considering Cseq, N₂O direct and indirect emissions and Yield across pedo-environmental conditions.

2. Methods

2.1 The *Input Layer*

The *Input Layer* contains the variables referred to pedo-environmental conditions and SMS characterizing each case scenario, i.e., a combination of soil × climate × SMS (crop, fertilization, irrigation and tillage). The datasets from meta-analysis (WP2), long-term experiments (WP3) and process-based models (WP4) will be used to populate the *Input Layer*. Values of the trade-off components associated to case scenarios will be used to train machine learning algorithms in both versions of the Σ OMMIT index presented here (see section 2.3). Once trained, the index can be used to perform trade-off analysis of additional case scenarios where Cseq, N₂O, NO₃⁻ and Yield data are not available.

The list of variables constituting the *Input Layer* has been defined based on D2.1 Knowledge Gap Report (Table 1), and resumes the current status of advancement of WP5 activities. The list could be extended according to the datasets which will be made available from WP2, WP3 and WP4. The levels defining categorical variables referred to SMS will be adjusted according to the available input datasets.

Table 1. List of the variables characterizing the input layer of the Σ OMMIT trade-off index.

Column	Description	Unit	Choice	Use
Case_scenario	A unique ID of the case scenario	string	Free	Case scenario
SOMMIT_WP	Work Package of reference	integer	2/3/4/5	Case scenario
Latitude	Latitude	dec.deg	Free	Case scenario
Longitude	Longitude	dec.deg	Free	Case scenario
Country	Country of reference	choice	Free	Case scenario
Year_start	Start year of the reference period	YYYY	Free	Case scenario
Year_end	End year of the reference period	YYYY	Free	Case scenario
Soil_Clay	Clay percentage	%	Free	Input layer
Soil_Sand	Sand percentage	%	Free	Input layer
Soil_SOCini	Soil organic carbon at "Year_start"	%	Free	Input layer
Soil_MineralN	Soil initial mineral N	%	Free	Input layer
Soil_pH	Soil pH	unitless	Free	Input layer
Clim_Temp	Annual average temperature	°C	Free	Input layer
Clim_ET0	Annual cumulative reference evapotranspiration	mm year ⁻¹	Free	Input layer
Clim_Rain	Annual cumulative rainfall	mm year ⁻¹	Free	Input layer
Crop_Type	Type of cropping system	choice	Single stand; Intercropping; Multiple cropping	Input layer
Crop_Name1	Name of the major crop in the year.	string	Free	Input layer
Crop_Yield1	Yield of the major crop in the year	t ha ⁻¹	Free	Input layer
Crop_Perc1	Fraction of the year covered by the major crop	%	Free	Input layer
Crop_Name2	Name of the minor crop in the year.	string	Free	Input layer
Crop_Yield2	Yield of the minor crop in the year	t ha ⁻¹	Free	Input layer
Crop_Perc2	Fraction of the year covered by the minor crop	%	Free	Input layer
Fert_Org	Amount of organic fertilizer applied	t ha ⁻¹	Free	Input layer
Fert_OrgCN	Stability ratio of the organic matter	unitless	Free	Input layer
Fert_Biochar	Amount of biochar added to the soil	t ha ⁻¹	Free	Input layer
Fert_MineralN	Amount of mineral fertilization	t ha ⁻¹	Free	Input layer
Irri_Amount	Amount of water applied with irrigation	mm year ⁻¹	Free	Input layer
Irri_Type	Type of irrigation system.	choice	Flood; Drip; Rainfed; Sprinkler;	Input layer
Irri_Drain	Presence of the drainage system	choice	Yes/No	Input layer
Till_ResidInc	Residue incorporation	choice	Yes/No	Input layer
Till_type	Type of tillage system.	choice	Zero; Conventional; Minimum;	Input layer
TradeOff_SOCend	Soil organic carbon at "Year_end"	%	Free	Training
TradeOff_NOxg	Emission of gaseous NOx	g m ⁻³	Free	Training
TradeOff_NO3	Leaching of Nitrates	kg N ha ⁻¹	Free	Training

The pedological conditions are defined by five variables. They are soil texture data (sand and clay content, % of weight), pH (unitless) and initial soil C and mineral N content (%). The reference soil depth is set to 0.4 m, considered as the limit of top soil layers (Jamali et al., 2021). These basic variables are commonly reported in field experimental studies and available in public online databases (e.g., [ISRIC](#)). Environmental conditions are defined by three variables allowing to consider thermal conditions, evapotranspiration processes and rainfall deficit for potential vegetative growth (Trabucco and Zomer, 2019). They are the average annual air temperature (°C), the cumulative precipitation (mm year⁻¹) and

the cumulative reference evapotranspiration (mm year^{-1}). The effect of short-term weather conditions (frequent freeze-thaw cycles) and their interactions with specific SMS (an irrigation event at high temperatures) on N_2O emissions cannot be captured by these synthetic variables. This simplification can be overcome by computing additional agroclimatic indicators from daily weather data (e.g., number of days with temperature $< 0^\circ\text{C}$ or higher than 35°C), which can be retrieved from public online databases (Sparks, 2018).

The SMS considered in the *Input Layer* are the cropping system, and fertilization, irrigation and tillage practices. The type of cropping system is defined by one categorical variable, with three possible choices, i.e., single stand, and inter/multiple cropping. Two crops can be defined by their name (free choice which will require homogenization), time of soil cover (fraction of the year) and yield (t ha^{-1}). Fertilizations practices are defined by the amount of mineral and organic fertilizers applied (t ha^{-1}), the latter requiring the associated stability ratio (C/N ratio). The addition of biochar (t ha^{-1}) can be specified. Irrigation practices are defined by the amount of irrigation water (mm), considering four irrigation systems: flood, drip, sprinkler, and rainfed management. Tillage practices are defined by the choice of incorporating crop residues or organic fertilizations (Yes/No), and by the tillage depth, with zero, conservative (e.g. minimum or non-inversion tillage) and conventional tillage as options.

Case scenarios can be added to the *Input Layer* via an on-line google sheet (i.e., [WP5 template](#), Figure 2.1), which can be downloaded as .csv file and automatically populated by simulation model outputs. Each row of the WP5 template identifies a case scenario, which is characterized by i) a unique ID; ii) the WP from which the data have been produced; iii) the geographic characterization (latitude, longitude and country); and iv) the period of reference (start and end year of measurements or simulations). The variables listed in Table 1 can then be valorized. The last columns of WP5 template are dedicated to characterize the trade-offs components, and are needed for the training phase of the ΣOMMIT index (Section 3.2).

Case_scenario	SOMMIT_WP	Latitude	Longitude	Country	Year_start	Year_end	Soil_Clay	Clay percentage [% w/w]
id1	3	3,773822	50,985457	Belgium	1999	1999	25	
id2	2	46.1	-70.5	...	2000	2000	50	

Figure 1. Screenshot of the online WP5 template. The sheet 'case scenarios' allows defining the Input Layer variables (each column has a note with the relevant unit of measurement), the sheet 'metadata' contains a description of each column of the sheet 'case scenarios', and the sheet 'dropDownList' contains the available choices for some variables of the Input Layer.

2.2 The two versions of the Σ OMMIT index

Both versions of the Σ OMMIT index use the *Input Layer* to synthesize the trade-off value of a case scenario in a unitless number ranging from 0 (worst trade-off) to 1 (best trade-off). Cseq, N₂O emissions, NO₃⁻ leaching and Yield are the components of the trade-off assessment.

2.2.1. Version α – an expert-data driven trade-off assessment

The *Input Layer* is processed by four hierarchical aggregation layers which progressively synthesize the trade-off value of the case scenario into the Σ OMMIT index (Figure 2). The 1st aggregation layer implements Adaptive-Network-based Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS) to synthesize the *Input Layer* into a distinct set of I-level modules for each trade-off component, considering pedo-environmental conditions (*Soil, Climate*) and SMS (*Crop, Fertilization, Irrigation, Tillage*). MODA is used to derive the weighting scheme starting from the 2nd aggregation layer: I-level modules are composed into two distinct sets of II-level modules, corresponding to Cseq, N₂O, NO₃⁻ and Yield; II-level modules are aggregated into the III-level modules *Environment* and *Management*, which are finally composed to give the Σ OMMIT index.

Figure 2. Hierarchical structure of the version α of the Σ OMMIT index. The acronyms are explained in the List of Abbreviations.

2.2.2. Version β – a data-expert driven trade-off assessment

The variables of the *Input Layer* are used to train Variable Importance-Weighted Random Forests models (VIW-RF, Liu and Zhao, 2017), using normalized values of trade-off components as predictors (I-level modules). MODA is used i) to modulate the probability of features selection in VIW-RF according to experts' perceptions of trade-offs, and ii) to guide the aggregation of I-level modules into the Σ OMMIT index (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Hierarchical structure of the version β of the Σ OMMIT index. The acronyms are explained in the List of Abbreviations.

The default weighting scheme implies the climate warming potential of the different GHG part of trade-off components in both versions of the Σ OMMIT index. Envisaged users – policy-makers, extension services, researchers – will have the possibility to modulate the scoring weight starting from II-level modules in version α , whereas in version β also *Input Layer* variables can be weighted by tuning VIW-RF parameters, i.e., modulating the probability of features selection (see section 2.3.2).

2.3 Learn from the data: machine learning

2.3.1 Version α – Adaptive-Network-based Fuzzy Inference System

The 1st aggregation layer in version α of the Σ OMMIT index is constituted by an Adaptive-Network-based Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS, Jang, 1993). ANFIS belongs to a family of hybrid systems, called 'neuro fuzzy networks' inheriting the properties of both neural networks and fuzzy logic (Mathur et al., 2016). The advantage of neural networks is that they can easily learn from an input dataset, but they have the drawback of hardly attributing a meaning to the acquired knowledge. In contrast, fuzzy logic models cannot learn from the data, but their outcomes can be easily understood as they are expressed in linguistic rather than numeric terms, and assume the structure of IF-THEN rules. Linguistic terms (e.g., IF x is low AND y is medium THEN z is high) are associated with degrees of memberships, allowing an input variable ('crisp' set) to partially belong to more than a single fuzzy set. In ANFIS, the database (*Input Layer*) defines the membership functions applied in IF-THEN rules, and the reasoning mechanism performs the inference procedure by optimizing network parameters (Figure 4).

The basic ANFIS structure is composed by six layers and requires reference input-output data pairs to be trained. Each layer is composed by nodes in charge of a specific step of the fuzzy reasoning, i.e., the Fuzzification (LF); the Antecedent estimation (LA); the rule Firing Strength evaluation (LFS); the Normalization of the Firing Strength values (LNFS); the Consequent estimation (LC); and the final

Output estimation (LO). Part of the network nodes are adaptive (Antecedent and Consequent estimation), meaning that the node parameters can be calibrated by optimization algorithms to maximize the accuracy during training.

Figure 4. The extended ANFIS architecture. The graph represent an ANFIS system with two input variables (x_1 and x_2), two membership functions (favorable F ; Unfavorable U), all possible combination of rules between the fuzzy set elements (F_{x_1}, U_{x_1} , and F_{x_2}, U_{x_2}). C_1 - C_4 , are the consequent linear functions, and y is the final output of the ANFIS. LF, LA, LFS, LNFS, LC and LO indicate the layers where the fuzzifier is defined (LF), the fuzzy sets are evaluated (LA), the rule firing strengths are calculated with a product t-norm (LFS), the normalization of the rule firing strengths is performed (LNFS), the consequent values are estimated (LC) and finally aggregated in the ANFIS output (LO). Squares represent the adaptive nodes whose parameter can be optimized, circles indicate fixed nodes without parameters. The symbols Π , N and Σ stand for production, normalization and summation operations, respectively.

The 'Fuzzification layer' has a number of nodes equal to the input variables corresponding to I-level modules (Figure 1). Each node in this layer is a fuzzifier in charge to map crisp inputs, i.e., the original values of the variables, into fuzzy sets, i.e., values from 0 to 1. Each input variable is fuzzified by two sigmoid membership functions yielding its Favourable or Unfavourable membership value. Distinct ANFIS will be trained for Cseq, N_2O emissions and NO_3^- leaching.

The 'Antecedent estimation layer' evaluates the values of the membership functions. Two nodes are defined for each input variable, one for each membership set. A maximum of 2^n (2 membership functions and n input variables) rules can be used by the 'Firing Strength evaluation' layer, which has the same number of nodes than the previous layer. The output of this layer is the strength of the firing rule for each node, which is evaluated by the product t-norm operation. The 'Firing Strength values' layer normalizes the rule firing strengths computing the ratio of each rule firing strength to their sum. The next layer is the 'Consequent estimation', which is composed by the same number of nodes than the previous layer. Each node evaluates a first order linear function

$$O_i^{LC} = w_i * C_i = w_i * (p_0 + \sum_{j=1}^n p_j * x_j)$$

where C_i is the consequent estimation for the i^{th} rule, w_i is the normalized firing strength from 'Firing Strength evaluation' layer, n is the number of input variables, x_j is the j^{th} variable from the 'Fuzzification' layer, p_0 and p_j are the constant and the j^{th} variable parameters of the linear function. The last network layer is the 'Output estimation', which is composed by a single node that performs the sum of the outputs of the 'Consequent estimation' layer.

An example of ANFIS application in the 1st aggregation layer of the version α of the Σ OMMIT index is provided in Figure 5 and Figure 6. Let us assume that the I-level module for N₂O emissions is derived by two variables from the *Input Layer*, i.e., cumulative rainfall and average temperature. Sigmoid functions are used to derive a Favorable and Unfavorable membership from the 'crisp' values of these variables. These functions, whose shape can either be derived from the variable distributions in the *Input Layer* or defined according to expert-opinion, will synthesize the Favorable/Unfavorable memberships of each input variable in a 0-1 interval (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Methodological steps to perform the fuzzification of crisp values in version α of the Σ OMMIT index. An example of a Climate module composed by two variables is provided.

The ANFIS system aggregates the fuzzy sets into a single synthetic value and then iteratively calibrates the network parameters to minimize the errors (RMSE in Figure 6) in estimating 'crisp' values of N₂O, using fuzzified input variables.

Figure 6. Schematic procedure to calibrate ANFIS network using the fuzzified input variables as predictors of N_2O . Different iterations are performed (epochs), until a tolerance level of the objective function (RMSE) is reached.

At each calibration step (epoch in Figure 6), RMSE is evaluated until a tolerance level is reached. At this stage, the training of the I-level module for N_2O ends, and the same procedure is repeated for the other trade-off components. The FuzzyR package has been used for ANFIS training and testing (Chen et al., 2020).

2.3.2 Version β – Variable Importance-Weighted Random Forests

Version β of the Σ OMMIT index is based on the application of Variable Importance-Weighted Random Forests (VIW-RF, Liu and Zhao, 2017), which are an extension of the popular Random Forest proposed by Breiman (2001) (Figure 7). Random forest (RF) is a supervised learning method which builds an ensemble of Classification and Regression Trees at training time. RF has been successfully applied to solve a wide range of classification and regression problems and offers an immediate estimate of the importance of each predictors during training. Applications of RF in agriculture span e.g., from crop detection at large spatial scale (Ok et al., 2012) to crop yield forecasting (Jeong et al., 2016) to modeling geographical distribution of insect pests (Peters et al., 2011) and ecological rivers characterization (Kubosova et al., 2010).

Random Forest is particularly suited:

- to analyze highly multidimensional data;
- to achieve high accuracy levels;
- to reduce overfitting, thanks to the introduction of random factors in the algorithm development;
- to speed up the training phase, even with many predictor variables;

Figure 7. Schematic representation of RF algorithm decision process for classification. The instance, i.e., dependent variable, is processed by a high number of CART decision trees that predict (regression) or classify (classification) data. The class that gets the majority vote (classification) or the CART ensemble average (regression) is indicated as the result.

The following operations are needed to create a RF algorithm. Given a set of n data with related M predictors, the RF algorithm:

1. defines a sub-set m of predictors from the total amount of M predictors, where $m \ll M$;
2. defines a training data set, resampling data for x times from the n data via bootstrapping methods (default 63% of data);
3. uses remaining data (out-of-bag, default 37%) to evaluate the algorithm accuracy;
4. randomly chooses a $m \ll M$ number of predictors for each node ($mtry$, default $m = M/3$ for regression);
5. calculates the node of the CART tree which represents the best splitting of n data among m predictors;
6. further divides such node into daughter nodes, always following the best splitting method. In this way the CART tree is grown until its maximum extension, without pruning techniques;
7. creates the forest reiterating steps 4 – 6 for x times, which correspond to the total number of CART trees.

Once the algorithm is trained, RF can be applied in prediction mode on new data using input properties and rules that have been created during training. When run in regression mode, each tree uses a different sample of features, makes its own individual prediction and these predictions are averaged to produce a single result. Random Forests generate a variable importance score for each predictor, which is evaluated as the increased regression MSE (measured on out-of-bag samples, i.e., samples not used to grow a tree) when a predictor is randomly permuted.

The Variable Importance-Weighted version of RF (VIW-RF) has been used in version β of the Σ OMMIT index in order to integrate experts' perception in the trade-off assessments. While the original RF implementation randomly samples predictors at each node to identify the best splitting (step 4), VIW-RF has the capability to modify the probability of selection of predictors during training. The weights assigned by experts (see section 2.4) to different domain areas (I-level modules of version α) are used to assign importance scores for any variable of the *Input Layer*. Instead of sampling m with equal probability for each predictor, m is sampled using probability proportional to the importance scores, thus reflect the weighting scheme of the experts. Let us imagine VIW-RF as a human brain: the decision-

maker could shape the trade-off assessment towards the analysis of the effect of specific SMS, by increasing the probability of the associated variables to be selected when learning from the data.

2.4 Multi-Objective Decision Analysis

Multi-Objective Decision Analysis (MODA) is a process for making decisions suited for complex issues involving multiple criteria and parties affected by the decisions. The advantage of MODA is its capability to provide a ranking of alternatives with the assumption that no value judgments, no trade-offs and no decisions can be reduced to single-criterion problems. This method has been applied to integrate conflicting evaluation criteria of technical, economic, environmental and social nature from different stakeholders with alternative views and preferences (Siksnelyte et al., 2018).

The starting point of MODA implementation in both versions of the Σ OMMIT index are the Single Value Attribute Functions (SAVF), which are used to calculate an individual criteria score from the raw data. The values of the I-level modules (0-1) as outputs from ANFIS or from VIH-RF are taken as SAVF values in version α and β , respectively. Multi Attribute Value Function (MAVF) scores are computed using a vector of weights that multiplies each SAVF value by the relative measure of importance. The vector of weights is normalized so that their sum is equal to one.

2.4.1 Version α – Strong experts weighting

The weight of each module within an aggregation layer could be estimated by two methods: i) for I-level modules, it could be derived from the correlation between the i^{th} indicator and the output variable used in ANFIS training; ii) for II- and III-level modules, it could be assigned via experts assessment to consider their specific perception of system sustainability.

2.4.2 Version β – Light experts weighting

A weighted average scheme is used to aggregate I-level modules corresponding to trade-off components, based on expert opinion. Experts can also change the probability of variables selection during VIW-RF training by modulating the weight of *Input Layer* variables, either grouped in Environmental or Management domain areas (III-level module of version α), or in Climate, Soil, Crop, Fertilization, Irrigation Tillage domain areas (II-level modules of version α).

We used the MODA function implemented in the “*DecisionAnalysis*” R-package for both versions of the Σ OMMIT trade-off index.

3. Proofs of concept of trade-off assessment

Disclaimer: the CH₄ trade-off component is used in this example but will not be considered in next stages. Yield was not considered in this example but will be included in next stages. Results from the application of the Σ OMMIT index strictly refer to the case scenarios defined in the dummy Input Layer. Results are presented here for evaluating the feasibility of the proposed methodology to perform trade-off assessment and highlight improvement areas. The proof of concept of version α was presented in the webinar organized by WP5 on December 2021, whose web registration is available [here](#) for Σ OMMIT partners. The proof of concept of version β has been realized as an online dashboard and is available [here](#) for Σ OMMIT partners.

3.1 Generation of the dummy input layer

The two versions of the Σ OMMIT index have been tested using a dummy Input Layer (section 3.1), with the objectives to facilitate their comparison and highlight weaknesses and critical points in their implementation. The dummy input layer has been generated using the subset of the *Input Layer* variables reported in Table 2 and Cseq, N₂O, NO₃⁻ and CH₄ as trade-off components. Multivariate normal distributions have been generated using superimposed correlations between input variables and trade-off components (Table 2). A total number of 2700 case scenario have been generated using the *mvrnorm* function of the MASS R package.

Table 2. Variables included in the dummy Input Layer to characterize the case scenarios and correlations with trade-off components. The sign + or – indicates positive and negative correlations with trade-off components.

Name	Description	μ	Notes
Soil_Clay	Clay content	50	$\sigma = 20$
Clim_Rain	Annual cumulative rainfall	500	+ with N ₂ O, CH ₄ , NO ₃ ⁻ (r = 0.5) – with Cseq (r = -0.3)
Clim_Temp	Annual average temperature	15	+ with N ₂ O (r = 0.5) – with Cseq (r = -0.5)
Fert_MineralN	Amount of mineral fertilization	200	+ with N ₂ O (r = 0.7), NO ₃ ⁻ (r = 0.6) and Cseq (0.2)
Fert_OrgCN	Stability ratio of the organic matter	20	$\sigma = 3$
Irrir_Type	Type of irrigation system.	Random choice: sprinkler, flood, drip	
Till_Type	Type of tillage system	Zero (++) , minimum (+) , conventional (-) with Cseq	
Cseq	Amount of carbon sequestration	100	Superimposed correlations with input variables
N ₂ O	Nitrous oxide emissions	100	
CH ₄	Methane emissions	100	
NO ₃ ⁻	Nitrate leaching	100	

The following correlations were established:

- Rain was positively correlated with NO₃⁻, N₂O and CH₄;
- Cseq was negatively correlated with tillage operations;
- N₂O emissions and NO₃⁻ leaching were positively correlated with MineralN.

The correlation matrix resulting from the generation of the dummy *Input Layer* is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Correlation analysis of the dummy input dataset. Scatterplots representing internal relationship within the dataset are reported in the lower section of the matrix, data distributions are plotted along the diagonal and Pearson correlation coefficients are reported in the upper section of the matrix. Negative and positive superimposed correlations are highlighted by blue and red squares, respectively.

3.2 Version α – Webinar test with Σ OMMIT partners

3.2.1 Training the ANFIS networks (I-level modules)

Twenty ANFIS networks pertaining to the I-modules Climate, Soil, Fertilization, Irrigation and Tillage were trained using variables from the dummy *Input Layer* (Table 3) as predictors of Cseq, N₂O, NO₃⁻ and CH₄. The ANFIS parameters modulating the Antecedent and Consequent estimation layer were optimized during the calibration process using RMSE as the objective function.

Table 3 reports the input variables used for training the ANFIS networks, and the respective test of suitability for the use in the Σ OMMIT index.

Table 3. Input variables used for training ANFIS networks in the proof of concept. The last column reports the test of the suitability of ANFIS to be used in the Σ OMMIT index.

I-level module	Input variables	ANFIS test
Climate	Clim_Temp Clim_Rain	Training with two continuous variables, at least one correlated with the output
Soil	Soil_Clay	Training with one continuous variable with no correlation with the outputs
Fertilization	Fert_OrgCN Fert_MineralN	Training with two continuous variables with or without correlation. E.g., N ₂ O is correlated with MineralN, Cseq is not correlated with input variables
Tillage	Till_Type	Training with at least one categorical variable correlated with an output variable. E.g., Tillage was correlated only with Cseq
Irrigation	Clim_Rain Irri_Type Soil_Clay	Training with more than two continuous variables and at least one categorical variable.

A distinct ANFIS network has been generated and trained for each I-level module, leading to twenty ANFIS networks differing in the input variables and in network parameters values. A sigmoid shape was used to define all fuzzy membership functions. The values of trade-off components from all case scenarios were normalized (min max method) before training ANFIS networks. Automatic optimization has been performed using a hybrid learning algorithm based on the gradient method and the least-squares estimate. RMSE trajectories during calibration and validation epochs (i.e., iterative calibrations) are reported in Figure 9. No problems were encountered in ANFIS implementation and the calibration process was technically successful. However, ANFIS performances during training highlight some criticalities which have to be addressed and verified when real input datasets from Σ OMMIT WP2, WP3 and WP4 will be available:

1. The training phase could be prone to overfitting (e.g., Figure 9a).
2. The accuracy does not improve when there are no correlation between variables. This was expected as only some correlations were imposed in the dummy input dataset (e.g., Figure 9b and 9c).
3. Categorical variables need to be fuzzified using user-defined membership functions, and the implementation and parametrization in the current R package is critical.

Figure 9. Root mean square errors (RMSE, y axis) during the training (red) and validation (blue) phase of the Adaptive Neuro Fuzzy Inference System in subsequent iterations (epochs, x axis). The title of each plot indicates the III-level (Environment/Management), the II-level (Cseq, N₂O, NO₃, CH₄) and I-level module of the Σ OMMIT trade-off index.

3.2.2 Weighting the aggregation layers (II-, III-level modules and Σ OMMIT index)

The I-level modules estimated by the trained ANFIS networks were aggregated via MODA (Chapter 2.4). In this proof of concept, we set equally balanced weights to I-level modules within the same domain area (e.g, Soil = 0.5 and Climate = 0.5 for Environment).

The weights of the II- and III- level modules were set starting from an online survey conducted by seven Σ OMMIT partners during the webinar.

The weight of III-level modules Environment and Management was derived from the expected contribution of pedo-environmental conditions and SMS to the Σ OMMIT trade-off index, which has been scored from 1 to 10 by the experts (Figure 10).

Give your score to the expected contribution of environmental conditions and farmer management on SOMMIT index.

Please consider Carbon Sequestration, N2O and CH4 emissions and NO3 lisciviation.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
environmental conditions	<input type="radio"/>									
farmer management	<input type="radio"/>									

[Reset](#)

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Figure 10. First question of the survey: assigning weights to the Environmental and Management modules

The weight of II-level modules was derived by giving a score from 1 to 10 to the expected contribution of the trade-off components to the value of the Σ OMMIT index. (Figure 11).

Give your score to the expected contribution of the following variables to the SOMMIT index.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
N2O emissions	<input type="radio"/>									
CH4 emissions	<input type="radio"/>									
NO3 lisciviation	<input type="radio"/>									
Carbon Sequestration	<input type="radio"/>									

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Figure 11. Second question of the survey: assigning weights to the trade-off components Cseq, N₂O, NO₃⁻ and CH₄ (the latter will not be considered in next developments)

The results of the survey were analyzed (Figure 12) and the weights of the II- and III-level modules derived accordingly.

Figure 12. Results of the survey questions to assign a value to III-level (a) and II-level modules (b).

The results of the survey indicate a slightly higher expected contribution of Management (0.53) with respect to Environment (0.47) to the Σ OMMIT index (Figure 13). The Σ OMMIT partners participating to the webinar were more interested in highlighting the effects of N_2O (0.33) in the trade-off evaluation, followed by NO_3^- (0.29), Cseq (0.25) and CH_4 (0.13).

Figure 13. Hierarchical structure of the Σ OMMIT index weighted from the web survey. The weight of I-level modules was balanced within domain area. The weighting of II- and III-level modules were derived by expert assessment.

3.2.3 Results of the trade-off analysis

Results from the pilot expert survey

The capability of the Σ OMMIT index to perform trade-off analysis was inferred by comparing its values with results from a principal component analysis (PCA), followed by a hierarchical cluster analysis (Ward method, Euclidean distance criterion) on PCA results (Figure 14a), using the dummy *Input Layer* as input. The first two PC explained 54.4% of the total variance and were retained in the analysis. Four clusters were identified and the corresponding distributions of trade-off components were analysed via boxplots (Figure 14b). Case scenarios in Cluster 1 and Cluster 4 led to the highest and lowest Cseq, N₂O and NO₃⁻, respectively. Case scenarios in Clusters 2 and Cluster 3 mainly differed in Cseq (high vs. low) and N₂O (low vs. high).

Figure 14. Results from the principal component and hierarchical clustering analysis. Biplot representing the data distributions along the two principal components, with eigenvalues overplotted as blue dotted arrows (a); boxplot analysis of the distributions of CH₄, Cseq, N₂O and NO₃⁻ in the four clusters (b); qualitative assessment of the trade-off components (c). Cluster 1 = red, Cluster 2 = blue, Cluster 3 = green, Cluster 4 = orange.

The Σ OMMIT index was computed on the same 2700 case scenarios in the dummy *Input Layer*. Index values ranged between 0.37 and 0.6. None of the case scenarios obtained totally adverse (0) or excellent trade-off values (1). Concerning the contribution of the trade-off components of sustainability (II-level modules), N₂O and CH₄ top and least participated to the Σ OMMIT index value, respectively, according to expert-opinion (Figure 15a).

Figure 15. Σ OMMIT index values for all 2700 (a) and the best five case scenarios (b) in the dummy Input Layer. The colors refer to the II-level modules CH₄ (red), Cseq (green), N₂O (orange) and NO₃ (blue). Color tones refer to the contributions of Management (light) and Environment (dark) modules (III-level).

Σ OMMIT index values considering the four Clusters highlights the index capability to reflect the superimposed correlations between input variables and trade-off components. Index values decreased from Cluster 1 (better trade-off value) to Cluster 4 (worse trade-off value), whereas Cluster 2 and Cluster 3 obtained intermediate values (Figure 16). The trade-off values in Cluster 2 were close to Cluster 1, mainly due to the low and high weight of the II-level modules CH₄ and Cseq, respectively. The large contribution of Cseq reduced the gap between the index values in Cluster 1 and Cluster 2, despite Cluster 2 was characterized by higher CH₄ and N₂O. Similar considerations apply to Cluster 3 and 4, the latter being associated with higher CH₄ and NO₃⁻, but characterized by a medium level of Cseq with respect to Cluster 3 (low level).

Figure 16. Analysis of the Σ OMMIT index values by clusters of case scenarios. Boxplots represent the distributions of trade-off components (Cseq, N₂O, NO₃, CH₄) in the four clusters (a), the qualitative evaluation of clusters based on their values (b), Boxplot of distributions of Σ OMMIT index values in the four clusters (c). Cluster 1 = red, Cluster 2 = blue, Cluster 3 = green, Cluster 4 = orange.

Results from the scenario analysis

The feasibility of adapting the Σ OMMIT index weighting scheme to alternative users perception was tested by changing the parameters of the MODA aggregation layers (2nd and 3rd). The contribution of II-level and III-level modules to the Σ OMMIT index was adjusted to mimic stakeholders perception towards: i) increased relevance of Cseq (0.6) above all other sustainability components, and ii) enhanced relevance of the contribution of SMS with respect to environmental conditions (Management = 0.7, Environment = 0.3). The Σ OMMIT index demonstrated to react to alternative evaluation schemes by changing its values according to stakeholders expectations (Figure 17). The

analysis of the trade-off values highlighted that some case scenarios were top-ranked disregarding the weighting scheme adopted (1439 and 1709 in Figure 17b,f,j). The other top performing case scenarios were not consistent across alternative weighing schemes, proving the plasticity of the Σ OMMIT index in response to user needs and specific interests. The index values according to PCA-based clusters denote that changing the weight of Cseq (II-level module) had a higher effect than changing the weight of Management (III-level module), with respect to the webinar scenario. The modification of the contribution of Cseq decreased the differences between Σ OMMIT index values in Cluster 1 and 2, and in Cluster 3 and 4.

Figure 17. Evaluation of Σ OMMIT index behavior under different weighting scenarios. Index values in the baseline scenario (a-d), changing the weight of Management module (e-h) and changing the weight of Cseq (i-l). The weights of the modules are reported with an indication of the change with respect to the baseline scenario (first row). Index values and composition considering the best five (second row) and all (third row) case scenarios. Blues, oranges, reds and greens tones refer to NO₃, N₂O, CH₄ and Cseq, respectively. Purple rectangles highlight best case scenarios regardless the weighting scenario. Boxplots of Σ OMMIT index distributions in the four clusters are reported with different colors in the last row. Cluster 1 = red, Cluster 2 = blue, Cluster 3 = green, Cluster 4 = orange.

3.3 Version β – Feasibility test and online dashboard

3.3.1 Training VIW-RF (I-level modules)

Four VIW-RF models were trained using all the variables from the dummy *Input Layer* (Table 2) as predictors of Cseq, N₂O, NO₃⁻ and Yield (here, CH₄ has been substituted with Yield as CH₄ is no longer part of the analysis). At first, an equal weighting of all input variables has been tested, set as the reciprocal of the number of input variables (7). The training of 2700 case scenarios took less than ten seconds for each VIW-RF, trained with 1000 trees and default *mtry*. The results are shown as scatterplots in Figure 18.

Figure 18. Scatterplots showing the performance of the VIW-RF models trained with the dummy *Input Layer* variables to predict the normalized values of the four trade-off components.

The correlation between normalized values of the trade-off components and VIW-RF denoted a variable accuracy, with R^2 ranging from 0.44 for Yield, to 0.92 for N₂O. The different accuracy of the VIW-RF are due to the superimposed correlations in the generation of the dummy *Input Layer* (see section 3.1).

3.3.2 Weighting the probability of predictors selection during training

The verification of the effect of changing the probability of selection of predictors during training according to experts weighting has been tested using the VIW-RF for N₂O, which obtained best performances during training (Figure 17). Two alternative weighting schemes were tested (Table 4), by differently weighting macro-domain areas (Environment and Management) and specific domain areas (Climate, Soil, Fertilization, Irrigation and Tillage) as structured in the version α of the Σ OMMIT index. These weighting schemes reflected in the probability of dummy *Input Layer* variables to be selected when training VIW-RF models, and were representative of an environment- and tillage- oriented perception of the trade-off assessment (Table 4)..

Table 4. Alternative weighting schemes tested on the version β of the Σ OMMIT index. The probability of the variables belonging to the *Input-Layer* of being selected when training VIW-RF has been derived according to custom weights assigned according to a climate- or tillage- oriented scenario.

Typology	Definition	Weighting scheme of the scenarios	
		Climate-oriented	Tillage-oriented
Macro domain	Environment	0.8	0.1
	Management	0.2	0.9
Environment	Climate	0.8	0.2
	Soil	0.2	0.8
Management	Fertilization	0.33	0.1
	Irrigation	0.33	0.1
	Tillage	0.33	0.8
Input-Layer variables	Soil_Clay	0.16 (0.8 · 0.2)	0.08 (0.1 · 0.8)
	Clim_Rain	0.64 (0.8 · 0.6)	0.02 (0.1 · 0.2)
	Clim_Temp	0.64 (0.8 · 0.6)	0.02 (0.1 · 0.2)
	Fert_MineralN	0.06 (0.2 · 0.33)	0.09 (0.9 · 0.1)
	Fert_OrgCN	0.06 (0.2 · 0.33)	0.09 (0.9 · 0.1)
	Irri_Type	0.06 (0.2 · 0.33)	0.09 (0.9 · 0.1)
	Till_Type	0.06 (0.2 · 0.33)	0.72 (0.9 · 0.8)

Two VIW-RF models were trained according to the two scenarios, by weighting the probability of the dummy *Input Layer* variables to be selected when splitting a tree node in the training phase. The effect of the weighting scheme has been assessed considering the increase in node purity of each predictor variable (Figure 19). This measure quantifies the contribution of single predictors to the accuracy of the Random Forest considering the total decrease in node impurities from splitting, averaged over all trees. Mathematically, it is computed as the difference of MSE before and after all nodes where a single predictor has been used to split the tree. The higher the increase in node purity, the more relevant the contribution of the predictor to the accuracy of the Random Forest model. The underlying hypothesis is that the modification of the probabilities of being selected during training will have an influence on the relative importance of the predictors, which in this example are the variables of the dummy *Input Layer*.

Figure 19. Increase in node purity in VIW-RF using predictor variables from the dummy Input Layer and N_2O as dependent variable, according to three alternative weighting schemes, i.e., equal weighting and environmental- or tillage-oriented.

The VIW-RF implementation from (Liu and Zhao, 2017) reacted to alternative weighting schemes by modifying the relative importance of the predictors. However, strong predictors (MineralN) top-ranked in explaining the variability of N_2O across weighting schemes. The difference between MineralN (22.5) and environmental variables (Rain = 14.5; Temp = 9.6) was reduced in the Environmental-oriented weighting scheme with respect to equal weighting, as expected. The increase in node purity due to tillage remained low across weighting scheme, due to the low correlation of this variable with the dependent variable N_2O in the dummy Input Layer.

3.3.3 Online dashboard to perform the trade-off analysis

A prototype of online dashboard has been developed to perform trade-off analysis using the version β of the Σ OMMIT index. The 2700 case scenarios were used to train VIW-RF in predicting trade-off components, and a factorial combination of three weights (low, medium, high) for each trade-off component has been used to integrate them into Σ OMMIT index. The aim of the dashboard is to provide Σ OMMIT partners with a prototype of the tool which will be developed in the project to perform trade-off analysis. The version 0.1 of the dashboard has been realized with Microsoft PowerBI and is available [here](#). A screenshot of the dashboard is provided in Figure 20, with an explanation of its main functionalities.

Figure 20. Prototype of the dashboard to perform trade-off analysis in the Σ OMMIT project.

Users can modify the variables in the dummy *Input Layer* to see the effects of changes in pedological (C/N ratio and clay content) variables, climatic conditions (temperature and rainfall), and SMS (tillage and irrigation type, amount of mineral fertilizers) (panel A). Modifications in the variables in the *Input Layer* are used to execute the trained VIW-RF and modify the normalized value of the trade-off components (panel B). In the mock-up, the VIW-RF trained on the 2700 case scenarios were already executed, therefore only pre-defined options are available. Experts can modulate the weights of the four trade-off components (panel C), which are aggregated to compute the Σ OMMIT index (panel D). A streetlight visualization is proposed to facilitate the interpretation of the results of the trade-off analysis (panel E).

4. Conclusions and perspectives

The integration of fuzzy-logic, neural networks and MODA techniques showed potential to synthesize the relationships between input variables and trade-off components under study. The version α of the Σ OMMIT index presents an articulated hierarchical structure which allowed inspecting the contribution of each domain area to the final index value, while tracing back all the reasoning steps. On the other hand, this version does not explicitly consider the interactions between SMS and pedo-environmental conditions in training the neural network, therefore relies on a strong expert base. The version β of the Σ OMMIT index derives the value of the trade-off components by means of Random Forest models trained with all variables from the *Input Layer*. Expert reasoning is used to modulate the importance of input variables and to aggregate trade-off components in the value of the Σ OMMIT index (as in version α). This version explicitly considers synergetic and antagonistic effects among SMS, but is more data demanding to be trained.

Expert opinion has been successfully implemented in the proofs of concept. The index behavior agreed with forced correlations between variables, despite some limitations in ANFIS training were

highlighted. The customization of membership functions for categorical variables and the risk of overfitting during the training phase still need to be addressed in the next steps.

The proposed versions of the Σ OMMIT index are still flexible both in the variables composing the *Input Layer* and in the hierarchical aggregation procedure. The neural networks are automatically created based on the variables of the *Input Layer* which are used to compute I-level modules. This means that input variables can be removed or added according to specific requirements.

The independent calibration of I-level modules allows evaluating trade-offs of case scenarios characterized by a limited set of input variables. The inclusion of a case scenario in the training phase is conditional to the availability of trade off component variables (Cseq, N₂O, NO₃⁻, Yield).

The Σ OMMIT index has the potential to be distinctly trained using datasets from all the other WPs, however the homogenization of the *Input Layer* could lead to train it using all available data from literature review, long-term experiments and simulation models. Some considerations on the expected feasibility of the datasets to be used in WP 5 activities follow:

- datasets from WP2 resemble the requirements of the Σ OMMIT index, as case scenarios will be organized in single rows including both variables from the *Input Layer* and trade-off components.
- datasets from WP3 concerning measurements from long-term experiments will be used depending on the availability of input and trade-off components variables. Criticality: to handle biases due to the different duration of the experiment.
- datasets from WP4 composed by outputs from simulation models will be used to train I-level modules, and perform scenario analysis.

Ongoing WP5 activities focus on the training of the Σ OMMIT index using emission factors and methodologies provided by IPCC guidelines for the estimation of SOC change, N₂O emissions and nitrate leaching as core activity of Task 5.3. The following research questions will be investigated in the next activities:

- i) are the emission factors from IPCC guidelines (Tier 1 approach) capable to highlight trade-offs using the Σ OMMIT index?
- ii) are the Σ OMMIT index values comparable when data from IPCC guidelines and from other WPs are used?
- iii) Which are the knowledge domain areas where limits and weaknesses still remain and need to be addressed by higher Tiers methodologies?

Both versions of the Σ OMMIT index proved to be valid to perform trade-offs analysis, and the selection of one version will depend on the typologies of data which will be made available by the other WPs. The main difference in the two versions is the machine learning algorithms to be trained with variables from the *Input Layer*. The ANFIS network (α version) requires high level of expert knowledge to drive the definition of fuzzy functions, and the definition of input-output relationships could be a critical step leading to overfitting. Conversely, the Random Forest (β version) is a more robust approach for regression and is capable to handle complex interactions between variables, but it a massive data driven approach, thus requiring a higher amount of data to be trained.

The pro and cons observed in the proofs of concept allow envisaging further developments of the Σ OMMIT index, where the positive features of α and β version are merged. As an example, *a priori* knowledge could be integrated via fuzzy logic to pre-process input variables or/and trade-off components (Cseq, N₂O, NO₃⁻, Yield), before training Random Forest models to estimate I-level modules. This could allow maximizing the strengths of current versions, and mitigating some of their drawbacks (e.g., overfitting for ANFIS, data dependency for Random Forest).

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